

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Article on Labia Mucosa: A Significant Area to Design and Deliver of Drugs

Anshika Sharma*, Sumit Kumar, Yusra Ahmad

Pharmaceutics, Faculty of Pharmacy, Uttarakhand Technical University Dehradun.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 02 Sept. 2025

Keywords:

antihypertensive,
antipsychotic, hair follicles,
cartilage, bones, sweat
glands and presence

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17035029

ABSTRACT

The main aim of this article is to learn the basic anatomy histology, nerve supply, blood supply, muscle supply of the human lips. It also focuses on how the formulations can be design in order to deliver various class of drugs like antihypertensive, antipsychotic, etc. when lip skin is compared with normal skin it accounts for greater bioavailability with lesser side effects. As devoid of hair follicles, cartilage, bones, sweat glands and presence of numerous blood supply making it red, hence labial mucosa is expected to offer a great advantage to administer a drug for both local and systemic action. These all makes the labial mucosa a significant area for delivering of drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Translabial drug delivery system defines a system in which the absorption of drug moiety occurs via lips or mucosal membrane. Oral cavity is a better site and ease for the delivery of drugs. Hence, there are many benefits of the system over the other route of drug delivery such as oral route in which there are certain dilemmas i.e., first- pass metabolism and GI degradation, which ultimately reduce the bioavailability of some drugs. Whereas due to the ideal characteristics of labial mucosa, it has become an attractive fact towards the drug delivery system which includes many advantages such as duration of action can be increased and

prevent from digestive enzymes and rapid action of suitable drugs. As lips are those parts of the body of human being which are the most delicate and made up of thin layer. These are mainly composed of muscles, skin and mucosa, but there is no any bone and infrastructure in its composition. Mucoadhesive agents play key role in the development of the translabial formulation. Due to the natural origin of mucoadhesive agents, it is biodegradable and biocompatible. Hence, it avoids patient non-compliance in chronic patients. It is also getting more important because multiple modification can be done easily. By this both local and systemic action of drugs can be achieved and

*Corresponding Author: Anshika Sharma

Address: Pharmaceutics, Faculty of Pharmacy, Uttarakhand Technical University Dehradun.

Email : dimpals2000@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

also bypasses first pass metabolism reducing dose and side effect.

Translabial Drug Delivery System ^[3,4,5,6,7,8]

It is commonly known that lips make the external part of the mouth of living organisms as well as form the entrance of oral route for in-taking the food and other substance along with the production of voice. Due to the rich blood supply, lips appear to be red which consist then tissues below and also have less number of melanocytes than the individuals who have more melanocytes. Lips have dual properties, these provide both local and systematic effect when drug is applied on lips. After seeing ideal characteristics of lips, it has been found that lips have an important role in the formulation of translabial drug delivery system. Therefore, this system has distinct pros which include natural origin of mucoadhesive agents which are biodegradable and biocompatible. Hence, it avoids patient non-compliance in chronic patients. It is also getting more important because multiple modification can be done easily. By this both local and systemic action of drugs can be achieved and also bypasses first pass metabolism reducing dose and side effect. It is considered that

in near days, this system will soon flourish in drug's development.

Anatomy And Physiology

Generally, lips contain 3-5 layers. Lips are two full fleshy fold which surrounds orifice of the mouth. Skin, muscles and mucosa accounts for the composition of lips. Mouth is lined by stratified squamous epithelium leads to the arrangement of cells in layers. This also provide the promising chromosomal studies by taking oral smears. Starting from its unique feature, it is devoid of hair, sebaceous gland and bone which makes lips more flexible in nature. Mucosal tissue is translucent in nature and supplied by a number of blood capillaries it red. Typically, in medical terms upper lips and lowers lip are termed as labia superiors and labia inferiors respectively. The surface of two lips can be differentiated by skin, mucous membrane lining or simply lining. The Junction where the lips meet the surrounding skin of mouth area is known as vermilion border. Typically color of vermilion border is reddish The comparative figure between regular/normal skin and lip skin are shown below in figure no 1

Fig: 1

Histology ^[4,11]

Lips skin is comprised of epidermis, subcutaneous, orbicularis oris muscle and mucosa. Vermilion of lips is composed of non-keratinised squamous epithelium that covers a number of capillaries. Inner surface of lips is composed of non-keratinised and consist of stratified squamous epithelium whereas outer surface facing towards external environment composed of squamous keratinised epithelial cells.

Blood Supply ^[12]

facial artery of external non-terminal branches provide the blood supply to the stem of lips, labia superiors and labia inferiors. Later on labia

superiors and labia inferiors bifurcate and anastomose with their companion artery from the other side. The blood supply are showmn in figure 2

Nerve supply ^[4]

The maxillary and mandibular branches of fifth cranial nerves provide the sensory stimulation to the lips. The sensory innervation are provided by the branches of mandibular nerve via a mental nerve branch to the lower lip innervation of lip. Whereas the sensory stimulation to the upper lip is received by the branches of maxillary nerve through infra-orbital nerve. The nerve supply are shown in figure 3.

Fig: 2

Blood Supply

Fig: 3

Nerve Supply

Muscle supply ^[12]

Lips with acting muscles are the part of facial muscles and these muscles are emerged from the mesoderm of the second pharyngeal arch. Therefore, it is supplied by the 7th cranial nerve of the second pharyngeal arch. The facial muscles are innervated with specialized members of panniculus carnosus that have attachment with dermis and hence, overlying skin is wrinkle or dimple.

Different muscle acting on lips

- Essential oral sphincter of the oral orifice
- Buccinator
- Orbicularis orris
- Muscles act as anchor points for other several other muscle
- Modiolus
- Muscles that elevate the lips
- Levator labii superioris
- Levator labii superioris alaeque nasi

- Levator anguli oris
- Zygomaticus minor
- Zygomaticus major muscle
- Muscles depressing the lips
- Risorius
- Depressor anguli oris
- Depressor labia inferioris
- Mentalis muscles

Lymphatic drainage ^[9,10]

There is an unilateral lymphatic drainage in the upper lip which attaches and makes 5 primary trunks that pass to the ipsilateral submandibular nodes along with other drainage that also lead to the parotid lymph nodes. The lymphatics which are attached to lower lip form 5 primary trunks that further lead to bilateral submental nodes via central lip and unilateral submandibular lymph nodes through the lateral lip. Lips have first echelon nodes which are the submental, submandibular and parotid lymph nodes.

Properties And Function of Lips ^[9,12,13]

- Lips play key role in exhibiting the facial expression and emotion of individuals
- Devoid of sebaceous gland
- Devoid of hair follicle
- Absent of skin pigment which leads to visible of blood vessels appearing red in color.
- It is very elastic and pliable in nature due to absent of bones.
- Lips are very sensitive to touch, warm and cold due to number of nerve supply.
- With greater permeability therapeutic concentration can be achieved quickly as it contains non-keratinized squamous epithelium.

Advantages Of Labia Mucosal Drug Delivery System ^[9]

- Ease of application and termination of medication
- Allow localized and systemic action of drug formulation
- Avoid patient non-compliance for chronic patients.
- It can also be administered to unconscious patient
- Biocompatibility and biodegradability are key feature of labial delivery.
- Reduction in dose and decrease dose dependent side effect
- It has a great patient compliance due to its non-invasive, painless and simple application in comparison to parenteral route.
- It avoids hepatic degradation of drugs which offers an excellent result for systemic effect. Therefore, it has a high rate of bioavailability.

Limitations Of Labia Mucosal Drug Delivery System ^[1,4,14,15,16]

- Unsuitable for local irritants
- Drug, adhesives, or other excipients providing local arrhythmia, erythema or itching cannot be used.
- Small area featuring in dose limitations
- Peptide delivery is not feasible due to presence of peptidase.
- Drugs with half life having 2-8 hrs only used for translabial purpose.
- Drugs having unpleasant odor, taste cannot be given by this route rather it need to be masked.

Probable Drug Permeation Mechanism Through Lip Skin:

There are two pathways for the penetration of drug through lip skin:

a. Transcellular/intracellular transport

It is defined as the passage of drug's molecules across the lip skin epithelium.

b. Paracellular/intercellular transport

It is defined as the transport of drug molecules through junctions between epithelial cell of lip skin.

fig : 4 Mechanism of drug permeation

The permeation of drug through sweat ducts, hair follicles and sebaceous glands which collectively known as shunt route, is not possible due to the absence of hair follicles and sweat ducts in vermillion zone of labial mucosa.

Labial Secretions [1,17,18]

The submucosal layer consists of salivary glands which secrete mucous.

Composition of mucous

components	% of composition
water	95%
Glycoprotein and lipids	0.5-5%
Mineral salts	0.5-1%
Free proteins	0.5-1%

Labial Mucoadhesion or Bioadhesion [1,17,18]

The term bioadhesion represents the bond between any two biological surface or a bond between biological and synthetic surface. But, in the case of adhesive drug delivery, bioadhesion describes the adhesion between the polymer either synthetic or natural and soft tissues or gastrointestinal mucosa. When the bond is formed with mucus, the term mucoadhesion can be used synonymously adhesion. Mucoadhesion is used as a term to define a state in which two components, one is of biological origins held together for a long period of time with the help of interfacial forces. Generally, bioadhesion is a term which widely includes adhesive interactions to any biologically derived substance and mucoadhesion can be defined as the formation of bond with mucosal surface.

Mechanism of Mucoadhesion

fig : 5 Mechanism of mucoadhesion

Mucoadhesion drug delivery system includes various ways of drug delivery systems; they are as follows:

- Buccal delivery system
- Vaginal delivery system
- Rectal delivery system
- Oral delivery system
- Nasal delivery system
- Ocular delivery system

There is not yet a complete understanding available that how and why certain molecules are attached to the mucus surface, few steps are accepted in the process at least for solid system. There are certain theories which are proposed to comprehend the process for fundamental mechanism of adhesion. Firstly, mucoadhesion should have the capability to spread over the substrate in order to initiate the close contact and increase in surface contact promotes the diffusion of its chain within the mucus. Attraction and repulsion forces are a complexity in the mucoadhesion, and for successful adhesion, attractions should be controlled over it. Each step of mucoadhesion can be made easy by the nature of dosage form and how it takes. For instance, a substrate can adsorb by a partially hydrated

polymer due to attraction by water surface. It is more likely Mucoadhesion just by one theory, the process of Mucoadhesion cannot be described. There are four different mechanisms of Mucoadhesion to describe in different approaches:

- Dehydrated or partially dosage forms make surface contact with substantial mucus layers (typically particulates administered drugs into the nasal cavity).
- Fully hydrated dosages forms contacting surfaces with substantial mucus layers (typically particulates of many mucoadhesive that have hydrated in the luminal contents on delivery to the lower gastrointestinal tract).
- Dry or partially hydrated dosages forms contacting surface with thin/discontinuous mucus layers (typically tablets or patches in the cavity or vagina).
- Fully hydrated dosage forms contacting surfaces with thin/discontinuous mucus layers (typically aqueous semisolids or liquids administered into the esophagus or eye)

Theory Of Mucoadhesion ^[5, 6]

- **Electronic theory-** According to this theory, when contact is formed between adhesive polymer and a mucus glycoprotein network, then transfer of electrons takes place due to the difference in their electronic structures. This leads to the formation of double electronic layer at the interface i.e., when a positively charged polymer chitosan and negative mucosal surface interact with each other, it creates adhesion on hydration which provides an intimate contact between dosage form and absorbing tissue.
- **Adsorption theory-** This theory postulates that when an initial contact is formed between two surfaces, material adheres with each other due to surface force which acting between the two atoms in its surfaces. There are two types of chemical bonds which formed by these forces that can be differentiated as primary chemical bonds that has covalent nature and secondary chemical bonds that have various types of forces of attraction, with electrostatic forces, vander walls force, hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds.
- **Diffusion theory-** In this theory, when both the polymer chain and mucus mix with each other at a sufficient depth, they create a semi permanent adhesive bond. The depth at which polymer chain penetrates, diffusion coefficient and time of contact of mucus plays a crucial role in this process, in which diffusion coefficient relies upon the value of molecular weight between crosslinking that goes down significantly as its density increases.
- **Wetting theory-** This theory proposes that if there is a contact angle of liquids which is lower on the substrate surface, it has great affinity towards the liquid to the substrate surface. In the presence of liquid, when two substrate surface bring together in the contact with each other, liquid acts as an adhesive between the substrate surface.
- **Cohesive theory-** According to this theory, the intermolecular interaction amongst same molecules plays a vital role in the phenomenon of bioadhesion.
- **Mechanical theory-** This theory proposes that adhesion takes place due to the filling of irregularities on the surface by a mucoadhesive liquid. Additionally, this roughness enhances the interfacial area which considered as the most important phenomena for the process because of interactions which is available with the help of dissipating energy
- **Fracture theory-** This theory is widely employed in the study for the measurement of mucoadhesion. It determines the force which is required to differentiate two surfaces after adhesion is founded. And this force S_m , is most used to calculate the test of resistance to rupture by the ratio of maximal detachment force F_m , and the total surface area, A_O , included in the surface interaction: $S_m = F_m/A_O$

Since this theory is only preferred with the force to distinguish the parts. Hence, this is not concerned for the interpretation or diffusion of polymer chains.

Factors affecting Mucoadhesion ^[9,17]

Based on Polymer used	Physical factor	Physiological factor
Molecular weight	Ph of substrate interface	mucin turnover
Concentration	Applied strength	Disease state
Flexibility	Initial contact time	Presence of enzyme
stereochemistry	swelling	

Mucoadhesive Polymer ^[5,6] Classification

1. On the basis of source

natural	Synthetic	Others
Agarose	HPMC	PVA
Chitosan	CMC	PVP
Gelatin	Alkylcyanoacrylate	Thiolated polymers
gums	methacrylate	polyoxymethylene

2. On the basis of aqueous solubility

water soluble	water insoluble
HPC(water 38°C)	Chitosan
HPMC(cold water)	EC
Sodium alginate	PC

3. On the basis of charge

Cationic	anionic
Aminodextran	Chitosan-EDTA
Chitosan	Pectin
(DEAE)-dextran	Sodium alginate
TMC	Xanthum gum

4. On the basis of potential mucoadhesive forces

covalent	hydrogen bond
Polyacrylates	scyanoacrylate
Hydroxy acrylates	

5. Electrostatic interaction- chitosan

Formulation aspects of TLDDS ^[19,19,20]

There are various ideal properties which should be taken into account during the formulation of dosage forms:

- It should be non-toxic and convenient to use.
- It should be non-irritant and pleasant.
- It should not dry the skin of lips and should easily remove with the help of water.
- It should be safe, economical and reliable.
- It should be easily applicable and removal along with its bioavailability property.

- It should deliver the drug effectively and release medicament easily.
- It should have a good homogeneity and having low sensitization index.
- It should be compatible with mucosa and lip skin and should not affect the functioning of lip skin.

Various identified dosage form of translabial drug delivery system

- Lipstick
- Lip rouge
- Lip varnish
- Lip jelly
- Lip salve (lip balm)
- Lip gloss
- Lip pencil
- Lip stain
- Lip liner
- Biostrip
- Bio flexy film
- Mucosal patches

Evaluation Parameter

- **Physical appearance-** colour, clarity, smoothness are visually inspected in order to ensure uniformity in appearance of formulation.
- **Weight uniformity** ^[22,23]- formulation is weigh on a digital balance and mean will be calculated.

- **Thickness** ^[21] - Three specific random formulations are taken and their thickness will be determined using micrometer screw gauge. Their mean will be calculated.
- **Folding endurance** ^[24,25] biolayers are subjected to repeatedly folding at the same place till it breaks. The number of folding it takes to break is a folding endurance of biolayers.
- **Swelling index** ^[23,26] - weigh a biolayers on coverslip and place it in a culture dish containing 10 ml of suitable buffer. After 1 hour, weigh the coverslip with the biolayers. The difference in the weight accounts for the absorption of water and swelling of biolayer.
- **Thickness** ^[21] - Three specific random formulations are taken and their thickness will be determined using micrometer screw gauge. Their mean will be calculated.
- **Skin irritancy test** ^[23,28] - It is done on anaesthetized animal like rabbit by following standard guideline. Carryout the study for at least 7 days and grade the application sites for redness, erythematic or irritation visually
- **Invivo release study** ^[23,26] - Apply the biolayer lips to the lip of anaesthetized rabbit. Collect the blood samples from ear vein at predetermined interval of time to calculate plasma drug concentration and various pharmacokinetic methods are calculated. AUC can also be calculated.

The swelling is given by

$S\% = (X_t - X_0) * 100$ Where, X_t = weight of swollen biostrip after time t X_0 = initial weight of biostrip.

- **Percentage moisture absorption** ^[22,27] - Take a biostrip (1cm²) into a watch glass and place in a desiccator containing a saturated solution of aluminium chloride for 72 hr. The percentage moisture absorption is given by:

$$\text{Moisture absorption \%} = \left[\frac{\text{final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \right] * 100$$

- **Percentage moisture loss** ^[28,29,30] - Take a biostrip (1cm²) into a watch glass and place in a desiccator containing a fused anhydrous calcium chloride for 72 hr. Then weight loss will be determined. The percentage moisture absorption is given by:

$$\text{Moisture loss \%} = \left[\frac{\text{final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \right] * 100$$

- **Surface PH study** ^[22,23] - Glass electrode can be used to find the ph. Allow the biolayers in

contact with 0.5 ml of distilled water for 1 hr at room temperature. Bring the electrode in contact with the surface of the biolayer and equilibrate it for 1 min. Calculate a ph value.

- **Stability studies** ^[21,23] - wrap the biolayer in aluminium foil and pack them in glass vials. Keep these in an incubator (stability study chamber) maintained at 40±2°C and 75±5% RH for 6 months. And observe change in physical characteristics and study release behaviour of stored biolayers

Applications

Although there is no any formulation available in the market, some of the articles shown the application in these types of drugs. This delivery system is generally used for the treatment of lip disorder. Medicated lip roughe containing niosomal acyclovir for the management of recurrent herpes labialis. Anti- diabetic drugs can also be given by this method.

CONCLUSION

The anatomy and histology of skin is different than normal skin. Since it is supplied by vascular and lymphatic drainage making to act drug for longer duration of action. It also reduces the dose and side effect. When translabial route is compared with

other route it provide far better various potential advantages. The research evidence signifies the translabial drug delivery system is a novel dosage form.

Future Perspective

Translabial drug delivery is potential novelistic approach for the delivery of drugs for both local and systemic effect. Since it is a peculiar delivery system designing a formulation is becoming quite interesting. Systemic delivery of drugs using this labial platform has done yet i.e. no market formulations are available in the market which also lead the researcher to design formulation. In upcoming future labial dosage form like mucoadhesive tablet, patches, films, bilayers, nanosomes, microsomes, emulgels, etc loaded with API can be formulated for significant delivery of drugs.

REFERENCES

1. Srinivas R. Bhairy, Dr. JagadevappaI(2016), Translabial route: a novelistic platform for systemic drug delivery, *Int journal of innovative pharmaceutical sciences and research*.
2. N.V. Satheesh Madhav , M.S. Uma Shankar (2011), A novel smart mucoadhesive biomaterial from Lallimantia royalena seed coat, *Science Asia*
3. Sneha Sagar Sharma , Anjali Aji (2018), Labia Oris: A Realistic Platform for Drug Delivery, *Int journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical research*.
4. N. V. Satheesh Madhav, Abhijeet Ojha (2012), Labial Mucosa As A Novel Transmucosal Drug Delivery Platform, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*
5. Pranshu T, shaffi Khurana(2011), MUCOADHESIVE DRUG DELIVERY: MECHANISM AND OF EVALUATION *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*
6. Anjana Anil, Preethi Sudheer(2018), MUCOADHESIVE POLYMERS: A REVIEW, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*,
7. Puratchikody A, Prasanth VV(2001), Buccal drug delivery: past, present and future-a review. *Int J Drug Dev*.
8. Miller NS, Chittchang M, Johnston TP(2005), The use of mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery. *Adv drug deli rev*.
9. Madhav Satheesh NV, Yadav AP(2011), Lip: An impressive and idealistic platform for drug delivery. *J Pharm Res*.
10. Pinar YA, Bilge O, Govsa F.(2005), Anatomic study of the blood supply of perioral region. *Clinical Anatomy*.
11. BabakJahn-Oarwar MD, Keith Blackwell MD(2007), Lips and Perioral Region anatomy, *eMedicinemArticle*.
12. Krishnapriya, Ramesh k(2015)., Translabial route: As a platform for systemic drug delivery, *j. chem. Pharm. Res*.
13. Richard D.2010) text book of E-study guide for grays anatomy for students, third edition, Elsevier: churchil livingstone
14. Henzel MR,Loomba PK,(2003) Transdermal delivery of sex steroids for hormone replacement therapy and contraception. A review of principles and practice, *j. reprod. Med*
15. Kormic CA, Santiago PJ, Benefit risk assessment of transdermal fentanyl for the treatment of chronic pain, *saf*
16. Murphy M, Carmichael AJ(2000), transdermal drug delivery system and skin sensitivity reaction, incidence and management, *AMJ Dermatol*
17. Sachin NK, Bhattacharya A(2009)., basics and therapeutic potential of oral mucoadhesive

- microparticulate drug delivery system, *Int. J. Pharm. Clin Res*
18. John DS(2005), the basics and underlying mechanism of mucoadhesion, advance drug delivery
 19. Hilde B. Poucher perfumes(2000), cosmetics and soaps, 10th edition , springer science business media
 20. Sharma PP(2014) cosmetics- formulations, manufacturing and quality control, 5th edition, Vandana publication, Delhi
 21. Satheesh madhav, Abhay Pratap(2014),, design and evaluation of novel rosiglitazone loaded bio strips using novel biomaterial for systemic delivery through novelistic translabial route, *Indo-Am. J. Pharm. Res*
 22. Ojha, A. and Satheesh Madhav N.V. (2014), A smart film forming agent from *Phaseolus vulgaris*. *Guru Drone J. Pharm. Res.*
 23. Satheesh Madhav, N.V. and Yadav, A.P.(2013), Development and evaluation of novel repaglinide biostrips for translabial delivery. *Int. Res. J. Pharm.*
 24. V. kusum devi, s. saisivam(2003), design and evaluation of matrix diffusion controlled transdermal patches of verampil hydrochloride, drug devind sapharm
 25. Noha N., Nabila B(2003),, design and characterisation of mucoadhesive buccal patches containing cetyl pyridinium chloride, *acta pharm*
 26. Satheesh Madhav N.V. and Yadav, A.P.(2013) A novel translabial platform utilizing bioexcipients from *Litchi chinensis* for the delivery of rosiglitazone maleate. *Acta. Pharmaceutica. Sinica.*
 27. Ramesh G., Vamshi Y(2007), development of nitrendipine transdermal patches: invitro and ex vivo characterization, current drug delivery system
 28. Bottenberg p., cleymaet R(1991), development and testing of bioadhesive fluoride containing slow release tablet for ooral use, *pharm pharmaco*
 29. Goudanavar, P.S., Bagali, R.S., Patil, S.M. and Chandashkhara. S.(2010), Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal films of glibenclamide. *Der Pharmacia Lett.*
 30. Lodhi, M., Dubey, A., Narayan, R. (2013) Formulation and evaluation of buccal film of Ivabradine hydrochloride for the treatment of stable angina pectoris. *Int. J. Pharm. Investing.*

HOW TO CITE: Anshika Sharma, Sumit Kumar, Yusra Ahmad, A Review Article on Labia Mucosa: A Significant Area to Design and Deliver of Drugs, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 9, 140-150 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035029>